

THE IMPORTANCE OF ENGLISH WORDS IN YOUTH SLANG**Nasimov Jaloldin**Supervisor: candidate of philological sciences **Rakhimov Zokir**

Abstract: Learning a foreign language is inextricably linked with the study of the culture of native speakers. Teaching slang, idiomatic expressions and phrasal verbs in foreign language classes contributes to the students' vocabulary, understanding informal speech patterns found in media texts and everyday communication with native speakers, developing speaking and listening skills. As a rule, at a foreign language class, students improve their listening, reading, speaking and writing skills through various study materials. Even with these skills, you can fail to communicate with native speakers, read magazines, watch television programmes and travel to foreign countries.

Keywords: Slang, word, language, English, Uzbek

INTRODUCTION

To study slang at foreign language lessons is of great interest both for the teacher and for students. The practical value of learning slang is essential for university students as the knowledge of such vocabulary is highly important for successful translation activities [1]. However, learning slang is not suitable for all groups of students.

Moreover, if “urban students” [2] do not use slang in everyday communication or if a group of students has a sufficiently low level of language knowledge, studying this group of vocabulary should not be the focus of attention. However, if students are highly motivated to learn a foreign language, communicate with native speakers, travel around the world, then studying some of the most common slang words and idiomatic expressions is definitely necessary.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The purpose of the research is to carry out a comparative analysis of the youth slang as one of the subsystems of the modern Uzbek and English languages, to determine slang as a special expressive meaning of vocabulary, to explain the reasons and its functioning features. In addition, the ways and means of youth slang formation are considered. The choice of the research topic is conditioned by the wide use of slang by Uzbek and English-speaking youth and the opportunity to introduce the study of slang and idiomatic expressions in the educational program of supplementary qualification "Translator in the field of professional interaction".

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Slang is an important element of any language and culture and when students reach a certain level of language training, it is necessary to pay attention to this "less academic" form of English. Along with teaching slang, it is advisable to pay attention to idiomatic expressions and phrasal verbs. In our opinion, the most effective ways of learning slang and idiomatic expressions in foreign language classes are:

1) **Listening:** students need to learn to hear slang words and expressions used in different contexts. It is very important for students to hear and analyze slang words used by native speakers. Moreover, it is also important for students to listen to dialogues with spontaneous rhythm and speed and understand by ear how certain slang words are used. Depending on the topic of the lesson, you can work with audio recordings related to the appearance, studying at the University, household conversations, travel, etc.

2) **Videos and clips from TV series** are a very effective way to learn slang. The teacher can use a whole episode of a popular TV show or focus on individual scenes from movies or popular TV series. When watching a video or listening to a dialogue, students should pay attention to other details, such as body language or intonation. This will help to better understand the verbal context, slang words and idiomatic expressions.

3) **Role play:** when students learn a certain number of words and slang

expressions, they can be used in some role-playing games. For example, students can write a few words on the board and suggest a role-playing game scenario where they want to use these words or only one word depending on the situation. For example, buying a computer, visiting a doctor, going to a cafe, etc.

4) Written tasks can be diverse. The difficulty of written exercises depends on the language level of the group. For example, for Intermediate/Upper Intermediate level groups the teacher can give the following types of written exercises: fill in the gaps in the text (dialogue) with slang words (idiomatic expressions); replace by phrasal verbs; select a slang word from the synonyms, etc. For more advanced learners (First Certificate English) the following types of written tasks can be offered: read the text (dialogue) and convert it with slang words and expressions. Or vice versa, students are offered a text (dialogue) containing a significant number of idiomatic or slang expressions that need to be converted into a more academic form. When doing these exercises, students learn to switch from one register to another, replenish the active vocabulary, memorize slang words and expressions which they can later use in specific situations of communication. To justify the need to study slang or idiomatic expressions, the authors tried to find out the ways of youth slang formation and the reasons for its functioning. According to I. V. Arnold, slang is the most extensively studied area and one of the "most controversial segments of the language" [4].

Among the ways of the slang word-formation are the following:

- adaptation from other languages (primarily English);
- full and partial calquing (calque/semi-calque);
- translation (using standard vocabulary with a special meaning; using slang of other professional groups);
- phonetic mimicry;
- words in a figurative sense (metaphorization).

Currently, words adopted from other languages are the most numerous group of slang words.

CONCLUSION

When the adopted word penetrates into the Uzbek language, it is subjected to the inflection laws of the Uzbek language: so`rash (ask, beg) - aski, layklash (like) – layk bos, shoping (shopping) – shoping qilish (bozor qilish), shopagolic, friend (friend) – yaxshi ko`rgani, etc. In addition, cognate word - derivatives are formed: krezi (madness)

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